

Emerging Adults' Quest for Autonomy; Self-Authorship and Its Impacts on Students' Academic Productivity in State Universities in Cameroon

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Abstract: This study examined emerging adults' quest for autonomy; Self-authorship and its impacts on students' academic productivity in State Universities in Cameroon. A mixed methods research design was used and the sample was made up of 624-year 2 master students of 8 faculties. In selecting respondents and study sites or faculties for the study, a multi-stage sampling technique (purposive, simple random and stratified sampling technique) was used. The instruments used for data collection were a closed ended questionnaire and an interview guide for students. The content validity index was 0.96 and the overall reliability of the instrument was 0.955. Data was analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively and descriptive (frequency counts, percentages) and inferential statistics (Chi-Square) were used to analyze quantitative data while qualitative data was analyzed using thematic analysis. Spearman rho test was used to establish the relationship between self-authorship and academic productivity of university students. The findings indicated that there was a significant, positive and strong relationship between self-authorship and academic productivity with P-value <0.001 , far <0.05 . The positive sign of the correlation coefficient ($R=0.506^{**}$) implied that academic productivity significantly increased with increase in self-authorship. Findings have implications for pedagogic practices as teachers need to establish a friendly relationship with their students and build these officious traits in them. This encourages the active implementation of the student-centered approach to learning in which case the students' needs and interests are catered for, causing them to develop a sense of belonging, ownership and autonomy in their educational activities. Based on the findings, some recommendations were made to the effect that counselors should caution students, and enlighten them on the need to develop themselves and as well strengthen their belief that their performances can be improved upon their own actions and this will inject in the students an additional effort in their studies.

Introduction

Students' quest for autonomy is often highly anticipated during emerging adulthood and is key transition period from college to university as they look forward to new academic and social experiences. Smith & Wertlieb (2005) however believe that many students often have unrealistic expectations about university life, and that their experiences often do not match their expectations as the reality for many students is that, university is accompanied by several unfamiliar and challenging experiences. Students encounter a more demanding

workload, greater independence, and increased responsibility for managing their time, studies, self-care, and finances. Students often move away from their family home and live alone in university residence or off-campus housing to become autonomous, and this often disrupts their social networks and might as well affect their academic productivity. In addition, many students enter university/college at the age where they are leaving adolescence and entering emerging adulthood, a developmental period characterized by identity exploration, increased responsibility, and independent decision making (Arnett, 2000). Consequently, students who are transitioning from high school simultaneously experience an ecological and developmental transition when they begin university.

As a result of the multiple issues that accompany the transition to university, most students go through an adjustment period. For some students, this adjustment is extremely difficult as they face challenges while trying to adapt to new roles, new routines, and a new academic and social environment may lead to uncertainty about their ability to meet personal and family expectations, and the other requirements of their new life. The number of new challenges and the uncertainty about their ability to succeed in their new environment might negatively impact their social network which may lead to high levels of stress and anxiety and consequently low academic productivity. On the other hand, if students could adopt autonomous positive behaviours such as students' self-authorship, self-efficacy, volition and self-regulation, these virtues might enhance their academic productivity in school.

Conceptually, autonomy is seen as presupposing a sense of agency, and to include the capacity to make decisions and to exercise control over important areas of one's life (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Autonomy is generally believed to be related to the development of a sense of self and as assisting in the construction of a personal identity (Moshman, 2005, Nucci, 2001). Autonomy does not mean the freedom to do whatever one wants to do or freedom from all constraints. Rather, autonomy involves making meaningful decisions on significant aspects of life (Kabeer, 1999). Individuals are considered to be autonomous when they rely on their own judgment about how to act, and make decisions which cohere with their own values and personality and for which they are self-motivated. Such decisions result from reflective evaluation, beliefs, and a capacity that develops in contexts where people can be reasonably informed and well-educated and experience choice.

According to Maysless & Keren (2014) autonomy is a key factor in a successful transition to adult life consisting of behaviors (individual capacity to act independently from others), cognitions (including self-efficacy, which empowers individuals to take action in different areas of their lives), and emotions (bonds built with others). However, a major developmental task during emerging adulthood is the quest for autonomy which is an undertaking that includes; becoming independent with regard to individual emotions, behavior, values, responsibilities and finances. Developing a sense of autonomy helps the emerging adult to enhance value-based decisions in preparation for adulthood.

It is made up of a set of skills and attitudes that include the ability to reason, to appreciate different points of view, and to debate with others. In order to do these things, the autonomous emerging adult must have a sense of self-worth and self-respect, self-beliefs, self-determined and self-initiative. Self-knowledge is also important, including a well-developed understanding of what matters to him or her (Deci and Ryan, 2016). All these skills are vital prerequisite to enable emerging adults become academically productive. Weinstein and Ryan (2010) state that the quest for autonomy refers to the notion that individuals experience themselves as having been generally free and self-congruent over time. It emphasizes the formation of life goals that guide emerging adults in ways that reflect their "inward forces" such as; ability to belief in themselves and take initiatives.

Based on these views, it is believed that, in order to feel fully autonomous individuals, need to satisfy specific components such as freedom (to be free from external and internal

coercion or arbitrary limitation of options, and to be free to access, explore, express, and realize authentic to basic psychological needs (e.g., relatedness and competence), temperamental dispositions, interests, and talents (Assor, Roth & Deci, 2004). Deci and Ryan (2016) report that, learners need two components in order to develop autonomous capacities which includes; relatedness, and competence. Relatedness involves helping students relate learning to personal meaningful intrinsic goals in a caring and welcoming learning environment. Competence involves fostering students' self-authorship and volition that they can do the work and that the required tasks are within their reach.

In the same line, self-authorship can be defined as the internal capacity of one's beliefs, identity, and social relations. This internal capacity allows an individual to answer questions such as: Who am I? How do I know? Self-authorship captures this journey of self-discovery through the process of questioning, clarifying, and grounding individual understanding (Baxter Magolda, 2004; Pizzolato, 2007). It involves a shift from accepting knowledge from authorities to constructing one's own knowledge. That is, when others' perceptions no longer define personal identity; instead, the identity becomes defined by one's own internally constructed goals, beliefs, and values. Self-authorship is the process of internally coordinating one's beliefs, values, and interpersonal loyalties rather than depending on external values, beliefs, and loyalties (Eriksen, 2006). Through this process, young adults develop their internal voices to meet challenges (Baxter, 2009). Self-authoring one's life is an ongoing process and learning how to listen to 'our own insides' and how to consciously and responsibly make meaningful sense of self and world.

The skills and abilities associated with self-authorship would not only help graduates succeed in academics and the workplace, but also to develop goals and build relationships that are more satisfying at work and at home (Pizzolato, 2006). This is seen as these skills manage relationships, rather than being managed by them and would likely help graduates steer away from behaviors and decisions that would lead to negative outcomes, such as legal troubles or interpersonal conflict (Piper, 2006). Therefore, self-authored graduates would let their internal beliefs and values guide their understanding of truth reflect on how their actions impact themselves and others, and see their individual decisions within a context of goals and situations larger than the one in which they find themselves at the moment (Pizzolato, 2006). These are the kinds of internal processes needed by participants and leaders in a democratic, multicultural society. Self-authorship is clearly emerging as a developmental achievement that benefits individuals, and society at large. Promoting self-authorship development would thus, serve the interests of institutions of higher education as well as those of students (Evans, Forney, Guido, Patton, & Renn, 2010).

On the other hand, according to Ahlfeldt, Mehta and Sellnow (2005) academic productivity is linked to thriving completion of course work success and student's ability to overcome challenges and complete the courses they have to take to complete their degree. Therefore, successfully completing coursework is an important condition towards successful degree completion and should be studied as a means to promote students' academic success. It also measures students' goal directedness, investment of effort, regulation of their own learning, and use of time. According to Appleton, Christenson & Furlong (2008) having objective, appropriate emotional conditions, self-belief, volition, interest and satisfaction enhances students' academic productivity. It is extremely important to students as many of them are accustomed to achieving high grades.

It also measures students' commitment and investment in learning or school activities (Ahlfeldt, Mehta & Sellnow, 2005; Alrashidi, Phan & Ngu, 2016; Hart, Steward & Jimerson, 2011). It measures how much attention students pay to learning activities such as coming to class, submitting assignments, and listening to teachers' instructions (Hu & Ching, 2012). It also serves as a strong predictor of student learning and personal development (Carini, Kuh, & Klein, 2004; Murray, 2004). Academic productivity is significant in students' life as it

represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university.

Therefore, to be academically productive, the emerging adult must incorporate autonomous behaviours. Autonomous behaviours are self-chosen, concordant with one's intrinsic interests such as having input or voice in determining one's own behavior. Eccles and Gootman (2002) identified support for efficacy, self-authorship and volition as key features of positive youth development settings. Support for these factors enhances young people to become productive, such as participation in program decision-making and leadership. Gundy (2002) also confirmed the autonomous behaviours such as; self-esteem, mastery, self-regulation and emotional reliance as important factors that can propel young people to achieve their academic goals.

Statement of Problem

Productive young adults require different developmental tasks; forming independence in terms of decision making, creating an adult identity, accepting responsibility for decision making and pursuing education and/or vocational goals. Such students anticipate successful outcomes, have confidence in their social skills and anticipate successful social encounters. Those confident in their academic skills expect high marks on exams and expect the quality of their work to reap academic benefits. The opposite is true to those who lack confidence. Young people who doubt their social skills often envision rejection or ridicule even before they establish social contact. It is therefore important that, young people acquire the necessary knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable and productive development which propel them to be self-authored, internally grounded in what they believe as true and worthy of pursuit. Those who lack confidence in their academic skills envision a low grade before they even begin an exam or enroll in a course.

It has been observed that, most students upon graduation lack the skills and knowledge vital to be productive in the twenty-first century as some of them are vastly unprepared for employment and cannot take initiative for themselves. Furthermore, according to a growing number of worries from some parents, employers and universities, many students leave the University ill-prepared and cannot adequately adapt to the community as some even get involve into drugs, and school dropout. Unproductive behaviour during emerging adulthood is related to greater levels of stress, including restrictions on socialization or the shrinking job market leading them to demonstrate depression. It is also common to find young people today still largely depending on their parents and other family members for livelihood of which it is believed that, during this period, emerging adults can earn a job or build a career for themselves while still schooling. Most of this un-civic behaviour might probably be due to lack of self-focus or self-determined attitude, low self-esteem and self-perception on the part of the individual taking full responsibility of their own development. Hence, this study examined emerging adults' quest for autonomy; self-authorship and its impacts on students' academic productivity in State Universities in Cameroon.

Specific Objective

Specifically, the study seeks to examine the extent to which self-authorship influences academic productivity of emerging adults

Specific Research Question

To what extent does self-authorship affect academic productivity of emerging adults?

Specific Hypotheses

- **Ho:** Self-authorship has no significant impact on academic productivity of emerging adults
- **Ha:** Self-authorship has a significant impact on academic productivity of emerging adults.

Significance of the Study

The research findings will be significant to the following; counsellors, teachers, parents, students, and the government.

The findings of this study will provide school counsellors with knowledge to understand that emerging adulthood is a time of risk and this subgroup of adults are especially vulnerable and need special support to ensure that they will manage the transition to adulthood well. The findings will help school counsellors to develop effective guidance and counselling services to help students study effectively. Also, this study will help counsellors to orientate students as they engage in their career endeavour.

The findings of this study will guide the government especially the Ministry of Higher Education to devise strategies to assist students as they quest for their autonomy these can be done through scholarships and providing counselling services to assist students in difficulties. Furthermore, this study will assist government through the Ministry of Higher Education in designing school programs that will give students the necessary skills that will gain them employment immediately after training and this could be done through workshops and seminars.

Furthermore, the findings of this study will be of significance to students of higher institute of learning as it will identify and expose to the students the issues that affect their academic productivity as they quest for autonomy.

To researchers, this work will act as a spring board for other researchers to investigate the concepts of emerging adults' autonomy and academic productivity. It will therefore act as a base material for future research in this field.

Literature Review

Concept of Emerging Adulthood

Emerging adulthood is a relatively new developmental concept seen predominantly in modern, post-industrial societies marked by great diversity in terms of relationships, family, education, employment and residential dynamics (Arnett, 2015). Emerging adults are at a distinctive stage of development characterized by both a myriad of opportunities for growth and change, as well as life-impacting problems (Bergman, Kelly, Nargiso & McKowen, 2016). This period of growth from adolescence to adulthood is an important time of life in its own right and is also significant because it sets the stage for later adult life.

The concept of emerging adulthood can be traced in the first half of the twentieth century, then stretched out and got individualized during the latter part of the century. Arnett & Taber (1994) first introduced the term "emerging adulthood" in the article "Adolescence Terminable and Interminable: When Does Adolescence End"? They saw it as the period between the time individuals consider themselves "to have begun the transition to adulthood" and the time when they consider themselves to be fully adult cognitively, emotionally and behaviorally. From his own research with Americans in their twenties, Arnett (2000) found that the preeminent criteria for emerging adulthood was accepting responsibility for one's self, followed by independent decision making and financial independence.

At the beginning of the 21st century, Arnett (2000) proposed a new developmental stage, emerging adulthood (in the age group ranging from 18 to 29), arguing that this stage is

distinct from the periods of adolescence. To Arnett, emerging adulthood is seen as an extension of Erikson's (1968) psychosocial moratorium, a period during which individuals are free to explore and experiment with potential identity alternatives (Castillo, Schwartz, Zamboangaet, 2013). During this stage, young peoples' world perspectives are challenged as they are exposed to diverse settings and views.

Arnett (1994, 1997, 1998, 2000, 2001, 2003 & 2007) being the main proponent of this developmental stage, reiterated that, this stage is the time of life which begins from the late teens through the mid-twenties, with a focus on ages 18-25. This period is characterized by frequent change as various possibilities in love, work and worldviews are explored. Essentially, this is a time when individuals would likely consider themselves too old to be adolescents, but not yet full-fledged adults. Hence, this often makes them to explore a variety of possible life directions in love, work, and worldviews autonomously (Arnett, 2007).

According to Jensen, Arnett & McKenzie (2011) emerging adulthood encompasses 5 main dimensions/main features which includes; age of instability (an exceptionally full and intense period of life but also an exceptionally unstable one), age of feeling in between (neither adolescent nor adult), time of self-focus (individual does not really have to answer to others), age of possibilities (when hopes flourish, when people have an unparalleled opportunity to transform their lives), and identity formation.

Concept of Autonomy

There have been challenges in adequately defining and operationalizing the term autonomy (Vansteenkiste & Beyers, 2013). To address these challenges, Vansteenkiste and colleagues (2013) explored the construct on two distinct dimensions: 1) independence (i.e., behaving, deciding, and thinking without relying on others) and, 2) volition (i.e., acting upon personal interests, values, and goals). Also, Hertz (1996) believes that, the term autonomy is derived from the Greek words *autos* (self) and *nomos* (rule) that is, reference to self-rule or self-governance. This involves being one's own person or being able to act according to one's beliefs or desires without interference that are characterized by the presence of freedom, rationality, and consistency with one's own preferences. Also, it includes a wide range of meanings that includes qualities such as; self-rule, self-determination, freedom of will, dignity, integrity, individuality, independence, self-knowledge, self-assertion, critical reflection, responsibility, absence of external causation, and knowledge of one's own interest. These are all qualities that propel emerging adults to become academically productive.

Autonomy is a complex socio-cognitive system, manifested in different degrees of independence and control of one's own learning process, involving capacities, abilities, attitudes, willingness, decision making, choices, planning, actions, and assessment of individual goals. Autonomy is generally believed to be related to the development of a sense of self and as assisting in the construction of a personal identity (Moshman, 2005, Nucci, 2001). The notion of the self stands at the center of the discussion on the concept of autonomy which is define as a system of processes, such as volition, self-efficacy, self-determination, self-regulation, and self-direction (Beck, 2002; Ryan and Deci, 2017). As emerging adults' quest for autonomy, these processes enhance them to become academic productive. It is typically seen as presupposing a sense of agency which includes the capacity to make decisions and to exercise control over important areas of one's life (Ryan & Deci, 2001).

According to Prunkl (2002) autonomy is a notoriously complex concept, but it generally can be taken to refer to a person's effective capacity for self-governance. This means that the individual can act on the basis of beliefs, values, motivations, and reasons that are in some relevant sense their own. There are at least two fundamental aspects to this definition, each pointing to a different set of conditions that need to be fulfilled for a person (or action) to

count as autonomous; authenticity which includes beliefs, values, motivations, and reasons held by a person are in a relevant sense authentic to that person, i.e. not the product of external manipulative or distorting influences. The second aspect is agency that is, the person is able to act on their beliefs and values they hold. This implies that, they have meaningful options available to them, allowing them to make choices that are of practical importance to their life.

Concept of Academic productivity

The term productivity encompasses, an economic construct which involves; efficiency, output, motivation, performance, effectiveness, profitability, competitiveness, and quality (Buckley, Pass & Prescott (1988). However, in an academic perspective, it refers to how much attention students pay to learning activities such as coming to class, submitting assignments, and listening to teachers' instructions (Shernoff, Csikszentmihalyi, Shneider & Shernoff (2003). It serves as a strong predictor of student learning and personal development. An evaluation of students' academic productivity is necessary for teachers as it can assist in resolving students' learning difficulties (Levin, 2013). According to Fredricks, Blumenfeld & Paris (2004), a student's continuous engagement in learning serves as a factor predicting learning achievement at all levels. That means it is required to improve students' learning engagement at different levels.

Alrashidi & Ngu (2016). believes that, academic productivity can be measured by student commitment, investment, and attitudes toward school and school activities and relates to factors that are necessary for learning. That means that, academic productivity happens if students have positive attitudes toward learning activities, and they have good communication with teachers. Garette & Dussauge (2000) believes that the term is comprised of active participations in learning process, such as the ability to understand lessons, being attentive to learning, involving in cooperative learning, having eye communication-thinking-questioning, having idea exchange, being curious to know, seeking-interaction-analysis, as well as making time-efforts. It involves students' behaviors such as; participation in discussion with classmates, participation in class activities, asking questions, making comments, debating, and discussing on a particular learning problem, both inside and outside of classroom with classmates and teachers, as well as submitting assignments. Similarly, Johnson (2016) explain that academic productivity is associated with learner's interactions with different educational components, such as community, school staff, classmates, teachers, and curriculum.

Finlay, 2006 and Fredricks (2003) posited three interrelated domains that are related to academic productivity: emotional, behavioral, and cognitive productivity. Emotional productivity refers to students' attachment to their teachers and peers, as well as their feelings about academics and school in general. Behavioral engagement includes students' positive conduct, such as effort, persistence, concentration, attention, and contributions in class (Fredricks, 2004). While cognitive productivity comprises both motivation and learning strategies (Fredricks, 2004). Motivation includes students' investment in their learning, as well as an intrinsic desire to learn and master the material. Students who are cognitively engaged are able to self-monitor and evaluate their learning strategies.

Self-Authorship as a factors of Students Academic Productivity

Self-authorship can be defined as the internal capacity of one's beliefs, identity, and social relations. This internal capacity allows an individual to answer questions such as: Who am I? How do I know? Self-authorship captures this journey of self-discovery through the process of questioning, clarifying, and grounding individual understanding (Baxter Magolda, 2004; Pizzolato, 2007). It involves a shift from accepting knowledge from authorities to constructing one's own knowledge. That is, when others' perceptions no longer define personal identity; instead, the identity becomes defined by one's own internally constructed

goals, beliefs, and values. Self-authorship is the process of internally coordinating one's beliefs, values, and interpersonal loyalties rather than depending on external values, beliefs, and loyalties (Kegan, 1994). Through this process, young adults develop their internal voices to meet challenges (Baxter, 2009). Self-authoring one's life is an ongoing process and learning how to listen to 'our own insides' and how to consciously and responsibly make meaningful sense of self and world (Parks, 2009).

According to Magolda (2008) there are four phases on the journey for self-authorship which includes; external formulas-individuals allow others to define them, doing what authorities suggest, following guidance from others to be successful; cross-roads-where one realizes her dissatisfaction with being defined by others and recognizes the need to look within for self-definition; becoming the author of one's own life-ability to choose one's beliefs and live them out (not without challenges), some renegotiation of relationships, weighing their needs against others; and internal Foundations—at this level, individuals become grounded in the sense of who they are, develop a mutuality of relationships, recognize that ambiguity and external influences exists, and base life decisions on a strong inner core of beliefs and self-concept.

Magolda (2001) further believes that, in order to achieve a successful self-authorship, there must be an integration of three dimensions which are considered vital to a young person's productivity. These dimensions include; epistemological, intrapersonal, and interpersonal. The development of these dimensions of self-authorship is necessary for emerging adults to build complex belief systems, to form a coherent sense of identity, and to develop authentic, mature relations with diverse others.

The epistemological dimension is conceptually defined in terms of an individual's ability to seek out and construct new knowledge and make meaning. At this dimension, individuals are able to 'view knowledge as contextual; develop an internal belief system via constructing, evaluating, and interpreting judgments in light of available evidence and frames of reference (Kegan, 1994). According to Baxter (1998) it relates to the ability to perceive that, knowledge is socially constructed and the construct of self-authorship answers 'the how you know question'. This is when individuals consider their thoughts about 'the nature of knowledge' and that 'what was right or wrong was not an absolute' (Pizzolato & Ozaki, 2007).

On the other hand, the intrapersonal domain of self-authorship is the ability for the individual to have a degree of autonomy and be freed from an external authority. Magolda (2004) further identified the intrapersonal dimension of self-authorship as the individuals' ability to 'choose own values and identity in crafting an internally generated sense of self that regulates interpretation of experience and choices. Hence, it is seen as the development and understanding of one's beliefs, identity, interests, values, and goals (Pizzolato & Ozaki, 2007).

Interpersonal construct is the ability to maintain relationships with others, and interact with diverse perspectives while keeping personal autonomy (Magolda, 1998). Pizzolato and Ozaki (2007) referred to the interpersonal dimension of self-authorship as 'maintaining healthy relationships' with others. The construct is the 'capacity to engage in authentic, interdependent relationships with diverse others in which self is not overshadowed by need for others' approval, mutually negotiating relational needs and genuinely taking others' perspectives into account without being consumed by them' (Baxter, 2004). It is believed that, self-authored individuals are able to manage relationships based on their internal goals and values.

Hodge, Baxter and Haynes (2009) observe that, self-authored individuals become mindful of their abilities and skills to define knowledge and make decisions according to their internal beliefs and goals, able to consider multiple perspectives, able to give reasons or cite

evidence in support of new ideas, and able to balance and maintain relationship with others. In line with these observations, Pizzolato (2007) confirms that, self-authored individuals demonstrate such capacities including; an internal set of beliefs that guide decision making about knowledge claims, an internal identity that enables them to express themselves in socially constructing knowledge with others, and the capacity to engage in mutually interdependent relationships to assess others' expertise. According to (Brown & Barlow (2009) skills associated with self-authorship individual includes; critical analysis evaluation, formation of integrated identity, independent learning, development of mature relationships embracement and valuing of diversity, consideration of multiple perspectives, cognitive maturity, collaboration and deciphering of ambiguity

Theoretical Review

Theory of Self-Authorship Development by Baxter Magolda (2001)

In the context of her theory of learning partnerships, Baxter Magolda defines self-authorship as the capacity to internally define a coherent belief system and identity that coordinates engagement in mutual relations with the larger world. As Baxter Magolda (1998) engaged her participants regarding the developmental experiences in their lives, she identified similarities in their journey toward self-authorship. Baxter Magolda observed that, self-authored individuals become mindful of their abilities and skills to define knowledge and make decisions according to their internal beliefs and goals, able to consider multiple perspectives, able to give reasons or cite evidence in support of new ideas, and able to balance and maintain relationship with others. In line with these observations, Baxter Magolda, and confirmed that, self-authored individuals demonstrate such 'capacities' including; an internal set of beliefs that guide decision making about knowledge claims, an internal identity that enables them to express themselves in socially constructing knowledge with others, and the capacity to engage in mutually interdependent relationships to assess others' expertise.

The road to self-authorship-where an individual's internal voice emerges and asserts its authority begins with cognitive dissonance, perhaps even existential crisis that challenges the individual's assumptions about the self, social relationships, and the world. Baxter Magolda refers to such experiences of dissonance as "provocative moments." Achieving desired college learning outcomes such as critical thinking, cultural competence, and moral and ethical judgment depends on where students are on the journey to self-authorship. Baxter Magolda believes that, students who are not yet able to author their inner psychological lives often allow their external influence to derail their academic goals, jeopardize their identity development, or ruin their relationships. She also found that, her participants demonstrated an increasing commitment to an "internal voice" in response to the interrelated questions of "Who am I?" "How do I know?" and "What relationships do I want to have with others?" Based on the changing nature of individuals' responses to their annual interviews, Baxter Magolda found four distinct phases of self-authorship development: following external formulas, the crossroads, becoming the author of one's own life, and internal foundations.

In the first phase, following external formulas, individuals seek to accommodate the expectations and demands of others. At this stage of development, many young people's career plans reflect their reliance on external formulas, having been provided by parents, siblings, mentors, or older students. Individuals are able to develop their own responses to challenges and to reason autonomously, but may become insecure absent external validation and approval. External formula followers may use language that reflects their control over their lives, their commitment to a unique identity, and their independence, but only as mimics, emulating the behaviors of self-authored others.

Such language may also reveal a desire to portray the externally defined image of adulthood.

She believes that, students rely on external formulas to fit in and that, the characteristics of this phase were well suited for achieving short-term social goals, particularly for individuals who felt different from their peers. The priority in this phase is not to identify the best course of action or perspective, but to discern the course of action or perspective that is advocated by trusted individuals or authorities. This practice of relying on such a circumscribed circle of acquaintances for career information and other advice, as opposed to trained professionals, poses many challenges for emerging adults as they quest for their autonomy. Following external formulas makes individuals vulnerable to buying into stereotypes, even stereotypes linking to one's own culture limiting their ability to engage with diverse others.

Individuals shift from following external formulas into the crossroads as they recognize the inadequacy of reliance on the advice, expectations, and demands of others. Recognition may follow negative experiences, such as the derailment of career paths, failed relationships, a lack of fulfillment despite faithful adherence to external formulas for success, or exposure to conflicting but mutually compelling perspectives and values. The crossroads is defined by the realized need for internal sources of belief and definition. Faced with competing external interests, parental expectations, or unfulfilling career prospects, individuals recognize the need to assert themselves, to develop the means to manage these challenges rather than be managed by them. However, individuals in this phase lacking the internal mechanism to consider these challenges from an internal perspective, may adopt defeatist attitudes or turn inward, hiding their desire to act and reason in ways that honour their internal perspective.

Baxter Magolda suggests that, individuals may practice self-authorship cognitively but continue to rely on third-order consciousness in their interactions and behaviors, individuals in the crossroads begin to recognize their ability to articulate their own beliefs, and to make knowledge claims, but may lack the confidence to consistently assert their emerging internal voice into their behavior and relationships. These individuals decide when and how to act on their perceptions and beliefs based primarily on their assessment of how others would respond. For individuals at the crossroads, all that is standing between them and self-authorship is the decision to commit to their internal voice. This decision comes following what is called the provocative moment. Described by Baxter Magolda as the gateway to self-authorship, the individual's commitment to an internal voice indicates the experience of a provocative moment. The provocative moment results from the "jarring disequilibrium" experienced as external formulas fail to satisfy. In order to identify relationships between students' experience of a provocative moment and personal or situational factors, she established a relationship between individuals' refusal to follow unsatisfactory external formulas, and their subsequent attempt to discover new options and to develop their internal voice. Rejection of external formulas, such as parental expectations, unwanted romantic relationships, and the plan for school and career success allow individuals to look inward, their heart, their pride, and their independence. Once individuals committed to their internal voice, they began to author their own lives.

As individuals enter the third phase, becoming the author of one's Life, they begin to assert their internal voice in everyday life, take a more active role in constructing knowledge and managing relationships, and develop a more complex awareness of their sense of self. This is a phase of changes, as individuals renegotiate existing relationships and take new approaches to their work and careers. Magolda proposes a new-found awareness of their world and their reasoning processes. This awareness allows them to manage their world rather than be managed by it. For instance, Baxter Magolda describes young people at this stage as redoubling of their effort in the face of obstacles that might have daunted them in the past, exploring their faith in personal ways as opposed to going through the motions, and being intentional about assuming new family roles as they recognized their subservience to their family's needs and expectations. Hence, students' emerging internal voice compelled them to give back to their community and serve others, suggesting a total

commitment to their beliefs and values.

These behaviors reveal the individuals' commitment to developing an internal system for making meaning of oneself, relations with others, and knowledge. She states that, in the process of working toward more gratifying outcomes, individuals place increasing emphasis on incorporating self-knowledge and goals in their meaning making. In this instance, the individual has made up his own mind about the issue. Individuals in this stage describe his opinion as being rooted in deep feelings on the issue. However, the individual frames his position not in terms of values and beliefs, but in terms of historical and cultural precedence. This, too, is an aspect of becoming the author of one's life. Individuals in this phase may not have enough confidence to assert their internal voice on its own merits, an indicator that the convictions are in their heads rather than in their hearts.

The integration of cognitive complexity with the development of a more complex understanding of self provides the internal foundation on which to make decisions, manage dissonance, and understand one's identity. Individuals' internal voices, which tend to take the form of confidence in one's reasoning, skill in the previous phase, or authority, become belief systems more adaptable to external realities. Individuals becoming the author of one's life might commit to a self-authored position, but through logic and reasoning. Having internal foundations allows individuals to articulate the core values or beliefs that drive their behavior, using simple language rooted not in financial factors, timing, and precedent, but in terms of feelings, vision, and being able to tell which decision is right. The internal foundation led a sense of peace, and to the confidence and to make decisions that might not be popular or respected by family members, friends, or coworkers. Therefore, as students' quest for autonomy, their ability to confront social pressure in the pursuit of their college aspirations is made possible only by the confidence in their internally defined beliefs, values, and goals.

In this final phase of self-authorship development, individuals employ the same commitment to the internal voice as in the becoming the author of one's life phase, but with the ability to manage and embrace uncertainty, divergent perspectives, and ambiguity. Baxter Magolda describes this as the individuals' acceptance of life as it unfolds. Such acceptance led not to complacency, however, but to more confident engagement in careers, relationships, and their world. In the process of becoming authors of their own lives, individuals realize that, they could not control the external world; rather they could control how they made meaning of the external world.

However, having an internal foundation does not reduce decisions to instinctive, or "gut" reactions, but rather it allows for the careful consideration of how the opinions and needs of others fit, conflicted, or undermined established beliefs and values. Individuals in this stage are those whose internal voice guides their construction of knowledge, exploration of self, and relations with others, and who welcome new perspectives, but will reject the safety of following external formulas, but confident of their ability to manage the ambiguity and challenge of adult life. Such is the achievement of self-authorship.

As a critique of this theory, while Kegan (1994) and Baxter Magolda (1998, 2001) suggest that individuals who demonstrate self-authorship will not regress to earlier phases, some research contradicts this suggestion. Pizzolato (2004), for instance, found that, faced with sufficient "external hostility toward outward expression of their internal foundations, individuals can abandon their internal voice in favor of more immediately gratifying external formulas. In addition, Torres and Hernandez (2007) postulate that there is evidence that, individuals can progress to the next phase in one of the three domains, while lagging behind in the others.

This theory is relevant to this study in that, it is seen as a central goal of students in higher education in the 21st century. In terms of the dimensions of self-authorship, the desirable

21st century learning outcomes entails students to be responsible in their learning while taking responsibilities in terms of cognitive maturity (epistemological dimension), viewing knowledge as contextual, or as constructed using relevant evidence in a particular context. This is a necessary ingredient for achieving academic outcomes; integrated identity (intrapersonal dimension) the ability to reflect upon, explore, and choose enduring values; and mature relationships (interpersonal dimension); respect for both one's own and others' particular cultures, productive collaboration to negotiate and integrate multiple perspectives and needs. This theory lays the foundation in that, it requires complexity in defining one's belief system, a coherent identity, and mutual relations learning outcomes to promote self-authorship through multi-contextual analysis-college education, graduate education, employment, community and personal life and their influence on the development of self-authorship.

Self-Regulation Theory by Zimmerman (2000)

Self-regulation theory (SRT) by Zimmerman is a system of conscious personal management that involves the process of guiding one's own thoughts, behaviors and feelings to reach goals. According to Zimmerman, self-regulation consists of several stages and individuals must function as contributors to their own motivation, behavior and development within a network of reciprocally interacting influences. Human behavior and learning is regulated through internal and external influences. Zimmerman's cyclical model has served as a theoretical foundation for students to evaluate learners' self-regulatory processes within academic, non-academic and naturalistic settings.

To him, self-regulation is the ability to develop control over one's thoughts, feelings, cognition, motivation and actions within the external environment. This social cognitive view suggests that SRT is a social process that is influenced by personal (e.g., control over one's own thoughts, feelings, motivation and actions), behavioral (e.g., skills, practice, self-efficacy), and environmental factors (e.g., social norms, influence on others, access in community) in a reciprocal fashion. It is a cyclical process in which learners set their goals, use different strategies to achieve their goals, and monitor and evaluate their performances. Overall, it encourages students to take responsibility of learning by employing metacognitive, motivated, and strategic actions (Zimmerman, 2002).

He views the structure of self-regulatory processes in terms of three cyclical phases which includes; The forethought phase refers to processes and beliefs that occur before efforts to learn; the performance phase refers to processes that occur during behavioral implementation, and self-reflection refers to processes that occur after each learning effort. Over the past years, Zimmerman has focused their efforts on applying self-regulation to the academic achievement challenges faced by many underprepared high school and college students. The theory incorporates advances in cognitive science to help teachers engage their students more fully in the learning process. The theory portrays when students become engaged, they take greater responsibility for their learning, and their academic performance improves. Zimmerman's theory makes use of an ongoing series of feedback cycles that consists of three phases as shown in the figure, and the function of each process are described as follows;

Figure 1. Phases and Sub processes of Self-Regulation

During the forethought phase, learners set their learning goals which involve task analysis and self-motivation. During this phase, students learn to more accurately assess their academic situation and choose strategies that best address a specific learning challenge. They also set achievable short and long-term goals. They make specific goals for learning and make a strategic plan to achieve their goals. There are two major classes of forethought phase processes: task analysis and self-motivation. Task analysis involves goal setting and strategic planning. There is considerable evidence of increased academic success by learners who set specific proximal goals for themselves. Self-motivation stems from students' beliefs about learning, such as self-efficacy beliefs about having the personal capability to learn and outcome expectations about personal consequences of learning. Intrinsic interest refers to the students' valuing of the task skill for its own merits, and learning goal orientation refers to valuing the process of learning for its own merits.

The performance control phase emphasizes self-monitoring of performance by the learners. In this phase, learners implement the plans which were formulated in the forethought phase. Performance phase includes self-control and self-observation. Self-control has sub-processes including self-instruction, imagery, attention focusing and task strategies. Whereas, self-observation involves self-recording of personal events or self-experimentation to find out the cause of these events

The self-reflection phase highlights an engagement in self-reflection after performance. There are two forms of self-reflection phase processes: self-judgment and self-reaction. One form of self-judgment, self-evaluation, refers to comparisons of self-observed performances against some standard, such as one's prior performance, another person's performance, or an absolute standard of performance. Another form of self-judgment involves causal attribution, which refers to beliefs about the cause of one's errors or successes. One form of self-reaction involves feelings of self-satisfaction and positive effect regarding one's performance. Increases in self-satisfaction enhance motivation, whereas decreases in self-satisfaction undermine further efforts to learn. Self-reactions also take the form of adaptive/defensive responses. Defensive reactions refer to efforts to protect one's self-image by withdrawing or avoiding opportunities to learn and perform, such as dropping a course. In contrast, adaptive reactions refer to adjustments designed to increase the effectiveness of one's method of learning, such as discarding or modifying an ineffective learning strategy.

According to Zimmerman (2000) this view of self-regulation is cyclical in that, self-reflections from prior efforts to learn affect sub-sequent forethought processes (e.g., self-dissatisfaction will lead to lower levels of self-efficacy and diminished effort during subsequent learning). He believes that, learners' use of forethought, performance, and self-reflection phase processes enhance their fulfillment of purpose. For example, students who set specific proximal goals, are more likely to self-observe their performance in these areas, more likely to achieve in the target area, and will display higher levels of self-efficacy than students who do not set goals.

He also stated that, experts display significantly higher levels of self-regulatory processes during practice efforts than novices. The self-regulation profile of novices is very distinctive from that of experts. Novices fail to engage in high-quality forethought and instead attempt to self-regulate their learning reactively. That is, they fail to set specific goals or to self-monitor systematically, and as a result, they tend to rely on comparisons with the performance of others to judge their learning effectiveness. Because typically other learners are also progressing, their performance represents a constantly increasing criterion of success that is very difficult to surpass.

Furthermore, learners who make comparative self-evaluations are prompted to attribute causation to ability deficiencies (which are also normative in nature), and this will produce lower personal satisfaction and prompt defensive reactions. In contrast, the self-regulation profile of experts reveals they display high levels of self-motivation and set hierarchical goals for themselves with process goals leading to outcome goals in succession. Experts plan learning efforts using powerful strategies and self-observe their effects, such as a visual organizer for filling in key information. They self-evaluate their performance against their personal goals rather than other learners' performance, and they make strategy (or method) attributions instead of ability attributions. This leads to greater personal satisfaction with their learning progress and further efforts to improve their performance. Together these self-reactions enhance various self-motivational beliefs of experts, such as self-efficacy, outcome expectations, learning goal orientation, and intrinsic interest.

This theory is relevant to this study because of several reasons. First, the theory in itself is comprehensive and covers majority of the key processes that are relevant for understanding students' self-regulatory behaviors. It offers explicit definitions of the underlying self-regulatory processes within each of its three general phases and further elaborates on how different processes interact. All these processes enhance emerging adults as they quest for autonomy. Consequently, it has been employed in academic (e.g., preparing for an exam, problem solving) and non-academic (e.g. health, and work) settings within varied contexts. Furthermore, the theory explains in detail how students' cognitive processing operates while planning, performing and evaluating a task. A crucial aspect is the use of criteria and standards to set goals, monitor and evaluate their academic objectives. It also describes how students constantly monitor their activities against standards and use tactics to perform tasks in their quest for autonomy. Hence, Zimmerman's theory has demonstrated that, the greatest academic productivity occurs when students use skills to guide learning and instruction, or one that entails planning, evaluation, and adjustment of thoughts and actions.

Empirical Review

According to a study by Mohammed (2019) assessing doctoral student development of self-authorship: the epistemological, intrapersonal, and interpersonal growths in University of Dammam, Saudi Arabia. The purpose of this study was to assess to what extent current doctoral students developed self-authored perspectives, as well as to assess whether or not there was an association between the number of years in the doctoral program and the development of three dimensions of self-authorship (i.e., Epistemological, Intrapersonal, and Interpersonal). It is important to study the development of self-authorship in doctoral

students because such development is necessary for individuals to overcome the challenges they experience in doctoral programs. The importance of this study rests on the fact that self-authorship development may prompt doctoral students' ability to succeed in the completion of their doctoral degrees, as well as to meet the challenges of their future in academia. Methodology Forty-five doctoral students in a Teaching and Learning program were surveyed on three constructs: Epistemological, Intrapersonal, and Interpersonal. The Doctoral Students' Self-Authorship Questionnaire was developed by the author based on Baxter Magolda's theory of self-authorship development. Three level-two constructs of self-authorship were conceptually and operationally defined. Contribution There is no instrument available (i.e., a questionnaire) to assess the self-authorship perspectives of doctoral students. Although it is expected that, people will develop self-authored perspectives as they get older, it is unknown to what extent current doctoral students develop self-authorship.

The findings showed that, participants had advanced levels in all three dimensions and continued to develop towards self-authorship. However, results showed a non-significant association between years in the doctoral program and self-authorship development. In other words, although doctoral students spend many years in certain programs, this spent time does not contribute significantly to their development of self-authorship. It was recommended that, for Practitioners the current study suggested that, doctoral programs should investigate their students' development toward self-authorship and provides them with more opportunities to better improve their self-authorship. For Researchers, the findings suggest further research into the developmental opportunities available for students within doctoral programs that assist students' ability to develop self-authored perspectives. The findings supported the importance of assessing doctoral students' self-authorship as part of doctoral programs. Without the assessment of doctoral student development of self-authorship in their programs, less effort might be taken to address student needs in developing self-authorship. Future research may continue the study of self-authorship for doctoral students from different culture.

This empirical review broadens the understanding of the concept of self-authorship, its relevance on students' academic productivity. It also provides knowledge on the different ways in which self-authorship could be developed over time. But the study was conducted only on Saudi Arabian Doctoral students. The researcher is willing to fill the gap by conducting similar research on the quest of autonomy on emerging adults' academic productivity in all Higher Institutions in the Southwest region of Cameroon to show that self-authorship significantly influences the academic productivity of emerging adults. No previous studies have assessed emerging adults' self-authorship in this region therefore; this study is to fit that gap.

Another study by Baxter (2001) which study followed 39 individuals over a 14-year period beginning in 1986 as they began college. These students were traditionally aged and attended Miami university of ohio. The study began with 101 participants, whom Baxter Magolda followed for many years. By the fifth years of the study, 70 participants remained; by the tenth year, participants dropped to 39. Findings suggest that individuals generally do not achieve self-authorship until their late 20s or early 30s, when encounter with "real world" complexities prompt intellectual, moral and intrapersonal dissonance. Individuals began to build personal foundations and belief systems in their mid-20s, and in their 30s, they experienced contexts in which their foundations and beliefs could be used. In the field of student affairs, these ages roughly correspond with traditional entry-level and mid-level professionals.

Methods

Research Design

This study adopted a mixed method approach whereby both quantitative and qualitative techniques will be used to examine the topic under investigation. The researcher adopted this approach in order to gain in-depth understanding from the multiple sources of information during the data collection process. This will be done through the use of designed structured questionnaire as well as interviews. Interview and structured questions asked, may likely lead to more probing to enable the researcher get the subjective opinion of the respondents thus getting to the root of the problem.

As posited by Monyatsi (2002) the advantage of integrating the two approaches maintains a balance since qualitative research is strong in depth, while quantitative research can be extended to a larger population. The two methods are not mutually exclusive, but complimentary. Furthermore, the mixed method approach will be suitable because while the quantitative approach will be used to measure the relevance of autonomy on emerging adult's academic productivity, the qualitative approach will be used to elicit the opinion of emerging adults that are self-employed or youths' leaders.

The study adopted the sequential explanatory research design. As explained by Creswell (2018) the explanatory sequential design implies that the quantitative data are first collected, analyzed and findings are used to guide the designing of the qualitative instrument. This design necessitates the collection of opinions or views from a sample of respondents from population, considered representatives of the entire population and the result was generalized and extended to the entire population. It is also quick and will help the researcher to collect information in a short time span. Hence, undertaking the study sequentially was found to be a sensible and practical way of undertaking the research.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is that entity to which the findings could be generalized and from which the sample would be taken. It is made up of potential persons from whom data could be collected and it consists of target, and accessible. Therefore, the population of this study was made up of all the masters students in 8 state Universities in Cameroon which constituted 44618 students. This population was chosen because, the researcher wanted to have an in-depth opinion about the topic under investigation and also, majority of emerging adults are found in this level of higher institution of learning. Hence, the researcher needed varied opinions of the respondents.

Target population

The target population of this study was made up of 23749 year 2 masters students from the 8 states universities which includes; 3318 students from the university of Bamenda, 4152 from the University of Buea, 7108 from the university of Douala, 1601 university of Dschang, 1101 university of Maroua, 2629 university of Ngoundere, 3840 university of Yaoundé 1 and 5571 university of Yaoundé 2. Masters' students were targeted in that, most of the students in this level are in their mid-twenties and thirties and could best understand the concept under investigation.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample of this study was derived from the accessible population of the study and the sample size consisted of 624 year 2 masters students in the selected programs of the State Universities. This sample size was chosen proportionately based on the Krejcie and Morgan table. As for the qualitative data, 10 students' leaders were randomly selected from the University of Buea.

Table 1: List of sample Size

	Area	Faculty/Schools	Number of Students	
	Institution			Sample Size
1	University of Buea	College of Technology	84	70
2	University of Bamenda	Higher Institute of Transport and logistics	35	32
3	University of Douala	Institute of Fine Arts	126	92
4	University of Dschang	Faculty of Agronomy	130	97
5	University of Maroua	Institute of Mines and Petroleum	145	103
6	University of Ngoundere	College of Technology	251	150
7	University of Yaounde I	Institute of Technology	79	66
8	University of Yaounde II	Institute of Demographic Studies	18	14
	Total		868	624

Sampling Technique

The main sampling techniques adopted for this study included, the probability sampling technique, specifically the simple random sampling technique which was used to select 8 departments in each of these universities. This afforded every faculty an equal chance of being selected for the study. A proportionate stratified sampling technique was then used to get the number of students to participate per faculty and per level. This technique was used to ensure that, the sample size of each faculty and by level of study was proportionate to the population size of the faculty when viewed against the entire population. The accidental/convenient/opportunity sampling technique was adopted in choosing the students to participate in the study since this technique consisted of taking the sample from people who were available at the time the study was carried out to fit the criteria the researcher was looking for.

Instrument used for Data Collection

The instruments that were used for data collection were; the questionnaire and the interview guide. This is because, the study adopted the sequential explanatory research design whereby both quantitative and qualitative techniques were used in the study to examine the topic under investigation.

Questionnaire

A questionnaire was used to collect data for this study. The questionnaire was formulated by the researcher in consultation with the supervisor and the statistician who went through item by item, where irrelevant items were discarded. This questionnaire was based on emerging adulthood quest of autonomy and academic productivity. The questionnaire was used for data collection because it is less time consuming, it is less expensive and can be appropriately used to collect the desired data from the sample. At the beginning of the questionnaire, there is an introductory note stating the research topic and the purpose of the questionnaire. In this note, the researcher ended by thanking the respondents for the time spared to provide responses to the questions, and promised to keep their responses confidential and use them strictly for research purposes.

This instrument was specially designed for students and was made up of six sections (A, B, C, D, E and F). Section A consisting of ten items demanding the demographic data of the respondents and all the sections consisted of close ended questions representing the

concept of autonomy of the four specific objectives of the independent variable and the dependent variable. Sections A to F contained ten items each that are directed towards the verification of the specific hypotheses and the answering of the specific research questions.

The items were close – ended, with likert– type response options ranging from strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD). The likert-type close-ended items were used because of the ease of responding and the short time required responding. A four-scale response option of strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), strongly disagree (SD) according to the likert scale used, assigned weights of 4,3,2, and 1 for positive items and 1,2,3, and 4 for negative items. The respondents were required to indicate their degree of agreement with a tick (√) on the appropriate answer of their choice. The questionnaire was made up of 58 items. All of which is close-ended for the students to fill and the items were stated as follows;

Interview Guide

Also, an interview guide was used to sample the opinion of some students based on the research question under investigation which will be made of 4 open-ended questions. An interview guide will be used by the researcher to guide questioning for qualitative analysis. Luma (1996) says an interview guide is made up of oral questions asked by one person (the interviewer) to another or others (interviewee(s)), with a view of extracting facts from the respondent(s). The interview guide consisted of questions that required the respondents' explanation of their ideas for an in-depth understanding of their responses and it entails 17 items on the research questions.

Validity and of Instruments

Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) contend that a major concern in research is the validity of the procedures and conclusions. In this light, the instrument for data collection of this study was validated considering the construct, content and face validity, and the reliability. After drafting and constructing the instrument, it was reviewed by the student. Some typing errors were discovered and corrected. The instruments were again reviewed by the supervisor, some lecturers, peers and the statistician. Inconsistencies and typographic errors were noticed and were corrected, readjusted, modified and handed to some faculty staff for appraisal. After taking a look at the items, they were adjusted, formatted to meet the required specifications in terms of quality, size, style, and visibility and then reprinted. The supervisor then finally looked at the instrument and some visible errors found were corrected to give the instrument the proper outlook. The main issues scrutinized for the face validity concerned the physical presentation of the instruments, structure of the various sections, visibility of contents and general presentation of the instruments.

Content validity involves confidence that items comprising the measuring instrument are representative of the field which they intend to serve. In order to enhance content validity, the instrument was subjected for scrutiny by the supervisor and the statistician. This was done by the supervisor and the statistician by evaluating the content of questions based on their relevance to variables and stated objectives as well on the demographic characteristics. They were evaluated to see if they measure what they were intended to measure so as to give results that could stand the test of objectivity and reliability. Modifications were made and items were found to have a match between content of instruments and objectives after further scrutiny. Construct validity made sure that conceptual definitions of the study concepts or theories are in line with the operational definitions of variables or study indicators. The supervisor reviewed the draft questionnaire and ensured that the language was adequate and understandable, and much more important that the concept or terminology used met the standard, were unambiguous and really fit the theoretical and operational perspective of the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the field was first processed using EPIData 3.1 whereby, all the participants' responses were keyed, in accordance with each of the test items. During this process of data entering, the demographic information and the test items were coded with numbers to facilitate the data entering and the questionnaires were also be assigned with serial numbers. The reason for coding and assigning each questionnaire a serial number was to ensure that on the data base, one should easily trace the individual responses of participants and to carry out any verification in areas of uncertainty if arise. After the data were completely entered for all the participants, the data based were exported to SPSS version 25 for further consistency, data range and validation checks with the purpose to first identify invalid codes (data cleaning) with the aid of exploratory statistics.

After the data were thoroughly checked for possible errors, the quantitative data were analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The descriptive statistical tools used are frequency count, percentages and multiple responses set which aimed at calculating the summary of findings for each variable for a quick comprehension of the overall findings. To test the hypotheses of the study, the Spearman's rho test was used because the data for the variables were not approximately normally distributed based on the statistics of the test of normality assumption trend of the data. The testing for normality assumption of every data is very important in order to avoid committing the type 1 or 2 hypothesis errors thereby, using the right test.

On the other, the qualitative data derived from open ended questions were analysed using the thematic analysis approach with the aid of themes, and quotations. The themes refer to the umbrella words which capture the main idea of the participants' statements and the quotations are the direct words from the participants while quotations are the direct words from the participants. Finally, findings were presented using frequency distribution and thematic tables and on charts with all inferential statistics presented at 95% level of confidence interval with alpha set at 0.05 levels, accepting 5% margin of error.

Ethical Considerations

Ethics in research are norms for conduct that distinguish between acceptable and unacceptable behaviour of researchers. Educational researchers need to be sensitive to ethical principles because of their research topic, face-to-face interactive data collection and emergent design and reciprocity with participants. The research was conducted according to the ethical guidelines proposed by the University of Buea in their thesis guide line for research on informed consent, voluntary participation and confidentiality. The University of Buea, Faculty of Education granted approval for the research project prior to data collection by issuing an introductory letter to be presented at the research sites. In light of the above, ethical measure was observed throughout the investigation and issues addressed in the cover letter attached to each research instrument. In the case of interviews, the researcher explained to the subjects.

Prior to administering the instruments, the researcher read out the information on the consent form which introduced the purpose and reason for the study and contained guarantees of confidentiality was attached to each instrument. In addition, the subjects were also informed (in the cover letter) that their participation was voluntary and could be withdrawn at any time without consequences in any shape or form. In this respect, each participant gave his or her permission to be observed, interviewed or to fill out the questionnaire. Following the clarification, participants were given the option to discontinue participation if they so desired. All those that took part in the investigation were given assurance of full confidentiality and anonymity as required in research involving human subjects. According to Maseko (2002), researchers are ethically obliged to maintain a healthy relationship with each participant. The researcher respected this principle in the

course of conducting this study among other things, posing no physical, emotional, intellectual or social threat to the respondents' privacy. For example, participants were informed not to mention their names during the process of completing questionnaires. The use of offensive, discriminatory, or other unacceptable language was totally avoided in the formulation of Questionnaire and Interview guide questions.

Presentation of Findings

Demographic Data

Data were successfully collected from 621 emerging adults of Master's degree second year students giving a returned rate of 99.5%. The findings were presented based on the specific research questions that guided the study as stated in chapter one and hypotheses tested. All statistics were presented at 95% confidence interval with error margin set at 0.05.

Table: 2 Distribution of Emerging Adults by Demographic Data

Demographic data		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	346	55.7
	Female	275	44.3
Age range	21-25	222	35.8
	26-30	227	36.6
	31-35	172	27.7
Marital status	Married	38	6.1
	Single	167	26.9
	Divorced	21	3.4
	Courtship	395	63.6
Employment status	Full time	52	8.4
	Part time	238	38.3
	Entrepreneur (Own a small business)	254	40.9
	None	77	12.4
Main financial support	Financial Aid-Loan	10	1.6
	Financial Aid-Scholarship	35	5.6
	Family	339	54.6
	Self-sustaining	237	38.2
Extracurricular activities within the community	Church activities	169	27.2
	Volunteerism in NGO	314	50.6
	Club activities	112	18.0
	Volunteerism in civic activities	6	1.0
	Other community activities	20	3.2
Socioeconomic status	Low	292	47.0
	Moderate	322	51.9
	High	7	1.1
Current GPA/Average on a scale of 4	Below 2.0	0	0
	2.0 to 2.4	0	0
	2.5 to 2.9	53	8.5
	3.0 to 3.5	434	69.9
	Above 3.5	134	21.6

The table shows that, among the 621 emerging adults' sample, 55.7% (346) were male and 44.3% (275) female. Age wise, 35.8% (222) of respondents were within the age range of 21-

25, 36.6% (227) of respondents were within the age range of 26-30, and 27.7% (172) within the age range of 31-35. Based on marital status, 6.1% (38) were married, 26.9% (167) single, 3.4% (21) were divorced and 63.6% (395) were into courtship. With reference to employment status, 8.4% (52) were full time employed, 38.3% (238) part time employed, 40.9% (254) owned a small business (entrepreneur) and 12.4% (77) not doing anything except studies. Based on financial support, 54.6% (339) of the students get finances from their family, 38.2% (237) from self-sustaining activity, while a few of them 7.2% (45) are on financial aid loan/scholarship. Based on extracurricular activities involve in the community, 50.6% (314) were doing volunteerism in NGOs, 27.2% (169) are involved in church activities, 18.0% (112) into club activities and 1.0% (6) involve in other activities in the community. Based on socio-economic status, that for 51.9% (322) of the students is moderate, low for 47.0% (292) of the students while only 1.1% (7) came from background with high socio-economic status. Finally, based on GPA/Class average after it was converted on a scale of 4 for those whose class average is on 20, none of them had a GPA below 2.5 while majority of them 69.9% (434) fall within the range of 3.0 to 3.5 and 21.6% (134) have GPA of above 3.5.

Findings by Research Questions

The presentation of the findings started first with the dependent variable (students' academic productivity) before the independent variables that constitute the objective of the study. The findings were presented using frequency, percentages and mean with a cut-off point set 2.5 on a scale of 1-4.

Students' Academic Productivity

Table: 3 Appraisal of the Emerging Adults Academic Productivity

Statements	Stretched				Collapsed		Mean	Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	SA/A	D/SD		
I am active in school activities	309 (49.8%)	284 (45.7%)	26 (4.2%)	2 (0.3%)	593 (95.5%)	28 (4.5%)	3.45	A
I usually past in my courses	369 (59.4%)	221 (35.6%)	27 (4.3%)	4 (0.6%)	590 (95.0%)	31 (5.0%)	3.54	A
I am engaged in research work	388 (62.5%)	202 (32.5%)	27 (4.3%)	4 (0.6%)	590 (95.0%)	31 (5.0%)	3.57	A
I have competency skills	421 (67.8%)	168 (27.1%)	30 (4.8%)	2 (0.3%)	589 (94.8%)	32 (5.2%)	3.63	A
I always finish my school task on time	442 (71.2%)	166 (26.7%)	8 (1.3%)	5 (0.8%)	608 (97.9%)	13 (2.1%)	3.69	A
I always have good grade	452 (72.8%)	154 (24.8%)	12 (1.9%)	3 (0.5%)	606 (97.6%)	15 (2.4%)	3.70	A
I easily network with others	463 (74.6%)	145 (23.3%)	10 (1.6%)	3 (0.5%)	608 (97.9%)	13 (2.1%)	3.73	A
I always listen to teachers' instructions	453 (72.9%)	156 (25.1%)	10 (1.6%)	2 (0.3%)	609 (98.1%)	12 (1.9%)	3.71	A
I always submit my assignments	474 (76.3%)	135 (21.7%)	10 (1.6%)	2 (0.3%)	609 (98.1%)	12 (1.9%)	3.75	A
I always attend classes	522 (84.1%)	93 (15.0%)	4 (0.6%)	2 (0.3%)	615 (99.0%)	6 (1.0%)	3.83	A
Multiple Responses Set	4293 (69.1%)	1724 (27.8%)	164 (2.6%)	29 (0.5%)	6017 (96.9%)	193 (3.1%)	3.66	A

Figure: 2 Appraisal of the Emerging Adults Academic Productivity

Based on emerging adults’ academic productivity, in aggregate, 96.9% of them with an overall mean of 3.66 on a scale of 1-4 indicate that academic productivity is high while 3.1% said is low. Specifically, majority of respondents 99.0% (615) agreed to always attend classes. Also, 98.1% (609) of respondents agreed to always listen to instruction and do assignments. Similarly, 97.9% (608) of respondents agreed to always finish their school task on time, and easily network with others. In the same trend, majority of respondents 97.6% (606) indicate that they always have good grade. Furthermore, majority of respondents 95.5% (593) agreed to be very active in class with 95.0% (590) of students agreed to always past their courses and engage in research work. Finally, 94.8% (589) of respondents agreed to have competency skills.

Table: 4 Distribution of Academic Productivity of the Emerging Adults Demographic Information

Demographic data			Academic productivity		Total based on MRS
			High	Low	
Gender	Male	n	3402	58	3460
		%	98.3%	1.7%	
	Female	n	2615	135	2750
		%	95.1%	4.9%	
Age range	21-25	n	2164	56	2220
		%	97.5%	2.5%	
	26-30	n	2202	68	2270
		%	97.0%	3.0%	
	31-35	n	1651	69	1720
		%	96.0%	4.0%	
Marital status	Married	n	372	8	380
		%	97.9%	2.1%	
	Single	n	1615	55	1670
		%	96.7%	3.3%	
	Divorced	n	206	4	210
		%	98.1%	1.9%	
	Courtship	n	3824	126	3950
		%	96.8%	3.2%	
Employment status	Full time	n	516	4	520
		%	99.2%	0.8%	
	Part time	n	2330	50	2380
		%	97.9%	2.1%	
	Entrepreneur (Own a small business)	n	2442	98	2540
		%	96.1%	3.9%	
	None	n	729	41	770
		%	94.7%	5.3%	

Main financial support	Financial Aid	n	450	0	450
		%	100%	0.0%	
	Family	n	3233	157	3390
		%	95.4%	4.6%	
Self-sustaining	n	2334	36	2370	
	%	98.5%	1.5%		
Socioeconomic status	Low	n	2832	78	2910
		%	97.3%	2.7%	
	Moderate	n	3105	115	3220
		%	96.4%	3.6%	
	High	n	70	0	70
		%	100%	0.0%	

Distributing the emerging adults' academic productivity by demographic information, it was observed that irrespective of sex, age range, marital status, employment status, main financial support and socioeconomic status, majority of them with percentage ranging from 95.1% to 100% score high in their academic productivity. In other words, despite the demographic data of the emerging adults, they do not significantly differ in their academic performance.

How does self-authorship affect academic productivity of emerging adults?

Table: 5 Appraisal of Emerging Adults Self-authorship

Statements	Stretched				Collapsed		Mean	Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	SA/A	D/SD		
I have self-knowledge about myself	360 (58.0%)	213 (34.3%)	42 (6.8%)	6 (1.0%)	573 (92.3%)	48 (7.7%)	3.49	A
I have positive relationships with others	403 (64.9%)	180 (29.0%)	30 (4.8%)	8 (1.3%)	583 (93.9%)	38 (6.1%)	3.57	A
I reflect a lot before taking decisions	420 (67.6%)	169 (27.2%)	30 (4.8%)	2 (0.3%)	589 (94.8%)	32 (5.2%)	3.62	A
I take full control of my decisions in life	416 (67.0%)	186 (30.0%)	15 (2.4%)	4 (0.6%)	602 (96.9%)	19 (3.1%)	3.63	A
I make decisions based on situations	417 (67.1%)	190 (30.6%)	10 (1.6%)	4 (0.6%)	607 (97.7%)	14 (2.3%)	3.64	A
I am captain of my life	411 (66.2%)	194 (31.2%)	16 (2.6%)	0 (0.0%)	605 (97.4%)	16 (2.6%)	3.64	A
I adapt to the environment despite adversities	445 (71.7%)	164 (26.4%)	10 (1.6%)	2 (0.3%)	609 (98.1%)	12 (1.9%)	3.69	A
I have a strong sense of identity	452 (72.8%)	152 (24.5%)	15 (2.4%)	2 (0.3%)	604 (97.3%)	17 (2.7%)	3.70	A
I strive to learn new things	469 (75.5%)	140 (22.5%)	12 (1.9%)	0 (0.0%)	609 (98.1%)	12 (1.9%)	3.74	A
I am committed to my goals.	475 (76.5%)	140 (22.5%)	6 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)	615 (99.0%)	6 (1.0%)	3.76	A
Multiple Responses Set	4268 (68.7%)	1728 (27.8%)	186 (3.0%)	28 (0.5%)	5996 (96.6%)	214 (3.4%)	3.65	A

Figure: 3 Appraisal of Emerging Adults Self-authorship

With respect to self-authorship, in aggregate, majority of the emerging adults 96.6% with an overall mean of 3.65 have strong self-authorship while 3.4% do not. Specifically, 99.0% (615) of the emerging adults are committed to their goals with 98.1% (609) strive to learn new things. Similarly, majority of the emerging adults 97.7% (607) make decision based on situations with 97.4% (605) agreed to be the captain of their life. To elucidate, majority of the emerging adults 96.9% (602) take full control of decision in their life. Similarly, 94.8% (589) of the emerging adults reflect a lot before making decisions while 5.2% (32) do not. Finally, 92.3% (573) have self-knowledge while 7.7% (48) do not know their self.

Table: 6 Distribution of Emerging Adults Self-authorship by Demographic Information

Demographic data			Self-authorship		Total based on MRS
			Strong	Weak	
Gender	Male	N	3336	124	3460
		%	96.4%	3.6%	
	Female	N	2660	90	2750
		%	96.7%	3.3%	
Age range	21-25	N	2149	71	2220
		%	96.8%	3.2%	
	26-30	N	2169	101	2270
		%	95.6%	4.4%	
	31-35	N	1678	42	1720
		%	97.6%	2.4%	
Marital status	Married	N	368	12	380
		%	96.8%	3.2%	
	Single	N	1641	29	1670
		%	98.3%	1.7%	
	Divorced	N	210	0	210
		%	100%	0.0%	
	Courtship	N	3777	173	3950
		%	95.6%	4.4%	
Employment status	Full time	N	492	28	520
		%	94.6%	5.4%	
	Part time	N	2328	52	2380
		%	97.8%	2.2%	
	Entrepreneur (Own a small business)	N	2430	110	2540
		%	95.7%	4.3%	
	None	N	746	24	770
		%	96.9%	3.1%	
Main financial support	Financial Aid	N	444	6	450

	Family	%	98.7%	1.3%	
		N	3303	87	3390
	Self-sustaining	%	97.4%	2.6%	
		N	2249	121	2370
Socioeconomic status	Low	N	2781	129	2910
		%	95.6%	4.4%	
	Moderate	N	3141	79	3220
		%	97.5%	2.5%	
	High	N	64	6	70
		%	91.4%	8.6%	

Distributing the emerging adults’ self-authorship by demographic information, it was observed that irrespective of sex, age range, marital status, employment status, main financial support and socioeconomic status, majority of the emerging adults with percentage ranging from 91.4% to 100% have a strong self-authorship. In other words, despite the demographic data of the emerging adults, they do not significantly differ in their self-authorship.

Table: 7 Necessary Measures Taken by the Emerging Adults to Achieve some of their Goals based on Self-authorship

Themes	Quotations
Set priority	“I give priority only to the things I like”. “I will focus only on important stuff”. “I do only things related to my objectives”. “I am so confident about my goals and I do not just do things which are not relevant”. “Prioritize my activities”. “Paying attention only to vital activities”.
Devotedness to study	“I always spend more time studying”. “I study every day”. “I am always attending classes”. “I attend all lectures”.
Focus	“I am focus”. “Paying attention only to relevant things”. “I am more self-focus and guided”.
Self-belief	“I belief in my goals”. “Self-belief”. “By believing more in myself”
Planning	“Effective planning”. “By planning and doing relevant things”. “By effective planning”.
Commitment	“I am very committed”. “Commitment only to important activities”.
Time management	“I pay more time only the necessary things”. “I manage my time to study”.
Self-orientation and discipline	“I have self-orientation and discipline”

Furthermore, asking some of the emerging adults to explain the measures taken in relation to self-authorship to achieve some of their goals, many of them said they had to set priority as depicted in the statements “I give priority only to the things I like”, “I will focus only on important stuff”, “I do only things related to my objectives”. Furthermore, many also add that there were devoted to their study as explained “I always spend more time studying”, “I study

every day”, “I am always attending classes”. In addition to setting priority and devotion, some said they were focus on the things relevant to them as narrated “Paying attention only to relevant things”, “I am more self-focus and guided”. Also, some of the respondents said they had the self-belief in achieving their goals, had to plan effectively, had to commit themselves only to the relevant things, had to properly manage their time for study and had self-orientation and self-discipline.

Verification of Hypothesis

Ho: Self-authorship has no significant influence on academic productivity of emerging adults

Ha: Self-authorship has a significant influence on academic productivity of emerging adults.

Table: 8

Perceived Influence of Self-authorship on Academic Productivity of Emerging Adults

Test	Statistical parameter	Self-authorship	Academic productivity of emerging adults
Spearman's rho	R-value	1	.123**
	p-value	.	.002
	N	621	621

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), at d.f 619, cl of 95, r-critical value is 0.079*

Statistically, at df of 619, and confidence interval of 95, the r-critical value is 0.079 which is less than the calculated r-value of 0.123. By this, it implies that self-authorship significantly influences academic productivity of emerging adults (R- value = 0.123**, p -value $0.002 < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value implies that academic productivity of the emerging adults with increase in self-authorship. Therefore, the hypothesis that states self-authorship has a significant influence on academic productivity of emerging adults was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Self-authorship and students' academic productivity

This research objective intended to examine the extent to which self-authorship affects student academic productivity. Findings showed that there was a significant, positive and strong relationship between self-authorship and academic productivity of students. The positive sign of the correlation coefficient implies that academic productivity significantly increases with increase in self-authorship. Also, the strong positive sign of the correlation is an indication that students will be high achievers or perform well in their academics if they are self-authors of their academic endeavors. Furthermore, asking some of the emerging adults to explain the measures taken in relation to self-authorship to achieve some of their goals, many of them said they had to set priority, were devoted to their study, focus on the things relevant to them, had the self-belief, plan effectively, committed themselves only to the relevant things, properly manage their time for study and had self-orientation and self-discipline.

This finding is in accordance with Hodge, Baxter and Haynes (2009) who supported that, self-authored individuals are mindful of their abilities and make decisions according to their internal beliefs and goals, able to consider multiple perspectives, able to give reasons or cite evidence in support of new ideas. They are able to balance and maintain relationship with others. In line with these observations, Pizzolato (2007) confirms that, self-authored individuals demonstrate such capacities including; an internal set of beliefs that guide decision making about knowledge claims, an internal identity that enables them to express themselves in socially constructing knowledge with others, and the capacity to engage in

mutually interdependent relationships to assess others' expertise. Brown (2009) also reiterates that, skills associated with self-authorship individual includes; critical analysis evaluation, formation of integrated identity, independent learning, development of mature relationships embracement and valuing of diversity, consideration of multiple perspectives, cognitive maturity, collaboration and deciphering of ambiguity.

This finding is also theorized by theory of self-authorship development by Baxter Magolda (2001) who see self-authorship as the capacity for individuals to internally define a coherent belief system and identity that coordinates engagement in mutual relations with the larger world. In relation to this theory, self-authored individuals become mindful of their abilities and skills to define knowledge and make decisions according to their internal beliefs and goals, able to consider multiple perspectives, able to give reasons or cite evidence in support of new ideas, and able to balance and maintain relationship with others. As this can also be seen in the finding where the respondents demonstrate such capacities including; an internal set of beliefs that guide decision making about knowledge claims, an internal identity that enables them to express themselves in advent of the challenges they go through.

The finding of this study was empirically supported by Baxter (2001) who examined 39 individuals over a 14-year period beginning in 1986 as they began college in Miami university. By the fifth years of the study, 70 participants remained; by the tenth year, participants dropped to 39. Findings suggest that individuals generally do not achieve self-authorship until their late 20s or early 30s, when encounter with "real world" complexities prompt intellectual, moral and intrapersonal dissonance. Individuals began to build personal foundations and belief systems in their mid-20s, and in their 30s, they experienced contexts in which their foundations and beliefs could be used. This finding has similarity with the current study as most of the respondents were in their mid-20s and 30s some already living an independent life which means, they could make life decisions without the interference of others.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made to enhance emerging adults' academic productivity and was done as follows. Teachers should integrate students' perspectives and input in instructional decision engaging them in conversations about the importance of expected learning and why they are being asked to complete academic tasks on time. Also providing frequent and timely feedback and allowing students to move at their appropriate pace. This could help better integrate students' perspectives on their learning, and also allow them to better adapt in the learning environment.

Teachers should as well aim at delivering instructions in a way that maximizes the opportunity for the mastery of experiences where teachers should promote experiential and cooperative learning strategies and this will maximize the learning curiosity of students from teachers and from one another. Teachers should also promote activity-oriented classrooms as well as provide opportunities for a wider range of communicative experiences such as internship and project writing. Mutual interaction and verbal expression should enhance autonomous learning. Learners should be given plenty of opportunities to explain their ideas to their team mates and to lead the discussions

Also, teachers should incorporate Bandura's (1989) four sources of self-efficacy- mastery experiences, modeling, social persuasion, and managing physiological arousal-into the plan of a course and the design of classroom activities and instructors should consider developing the self-efficacy of students by incorporating approaches based on these four tools. Students should be provided with opportunities and tools to learn how to handle success or failure; to imitate high-achieving role models, to devise ways of overcoming obstacles.

Counsellors should engage students in goals articulation exercises immediately they get

admission into a program. Orientation teams can start with students the first time they come to campus by working with them in developing goals, and connect those goals to their daily lives and needs. Counsellors through student affairs units can build on those goal-setting activities and engage students in frequent reflections on set goals. Also, there should be a close collaboration between student support services and academic programs to foster students' autonomous motivation capacities in an autonomous supportive learning environment. An example of such collaboration could be for student affairs personnel and academic programs to develop ways to promote more intentional connections between the work students do out of school and the work they do in their academic programs, in order to support more lifelong autonomous goals.

Students should develop resilience and targeted initiatives to support their career. Initiatives to support students could include developing networks that allow them opportunities for early involvement in high impact practices, such as attending seminars, research projects or internships. High impact practices can support factors like socializing, connection with career choice, and closer collaboration with instructors or mentors. Also, students should be optimistic and develop realistic, meaningful, challenging and achievable goals that will help them develop a sense of direction and purpose. Such students perform well academically because they would be self-motivated and would probably manage easily without seeking help neither from peers nor from instructors.

Suggestions for Further Study

This study should be replicated on a larger scale to support or challenge the findings. In addition, similar studies should be undertaken at a variety of institutions and institutional types to see if there are differences in findings related to institutional type and in particular regions or area.

Much of the existing literature on autonomy assumes that it is not a common concept among students. However, the present study found that nearly all of the participants demonstrated autonomy. Therefore, a large-scale study should be undertaken to determine the extent to which college graduates have achieved autonomy. Such a study might utilize interview techniques focused on assessing students' predominant or optimal ways of approaching decisions, relationships, and identities as described in the study.

Also, further research is needed to determine the role that coping mechanisms play in students' academic productivity. Students' coping strategies appear to dictate their potential to become self-authored and productive.

Implications for Education and Contributions to Psychological Knowledge

There are some implications for practice from this research on the topic of emerging adults' quest for autonomy and students and academic productivity. Policy and practice decision makers need to pay particular attention on students' quest for autonomy is often highly anticipated during emerging adulthood and is key transitional period from college to university as individuals look forward to new academic and social experiences. Therefore, postgraduate programs should be designed to involve autonomous learning and provide students with opportunities that promote self-authorship. For example, the teaching and orientation practices should be designed to assist students to develop their internal identities, values and goals, as well as to encourage students to build and maintain positive relationship with others despites the challenges they go through.

Also, a comprehensive understanding of students' experiences focusing on self-efficacy, self-authorship, volition and self-regulation is warranted to provide a well-rounded perspective on the challenges faced by students in achieving academic productivity. Without this assessment, less effort might be taken to address student needs in promoting academic productivity. Hence, this research provided a tool that can assist in understanding the reality

of emerging adults in pursuit of academic productivity. Educators' awareness on this subject will help them to address it, therefore, the contribution of this study rests on the fact that, the quest for autonomy may prompt students' ability to succeed in the completion of their academic programs as well as to meet the challenges of their future in academia.

Limitations of the Study

Although this research was carefully prepared, we are aware of some limitations and shortcomings. Firstly, the researcher sampled participants from only public universities and this particular context might have impacted the results. Thus, knowing how students in other types of institutions experience remains limited within the scope of the present study.

Another limiting factor may have arisen based on bias associated with self-reported data. It is believed that, human tendency to overestimate themselves when prompted for self-assessment especially those that have to do with competence and thinking abilities might not paint a real picture about the individual.

Conclusion

This study explored how the quest for autonomy influence emerging adults' academic productivity. The study concluded that the level of autonomous variables score amongst the students is comparatively high. There is positive relationship between autonomy and students' academic productivity. Therefore, individuals who are more autonomous, are more productive academically. They believe that they have all the determination to deal with their own lives, that their own measures and decision-making have an effect on their lives, whilst those with low level of autonomy are considerably poorer in academic productivity. Emerging adults with better autonomy are more likely to make attempts to achieve a goal or task, and to endure longer in those attempts, than individuals with poor autonomy.

Therefore, the findings of this study will contribute to higher education and to the literature pertaining to higher education. It therefore, provides insight into the perception of emerging adults college experience and direction for possible programs and policies. The findings have implications for the leaders within higher education institutions as universities can promote self-directed and lifelong learning by developing and promoting autonomous supported learning environments through experiential learning. This is contended that one of the dilemmas facing current learning environments is what could be referred to as a mismatch between autonomous behaviour of students and their academic productivity. Therefore, higher education institutions can promote learners' autonomous capabilities by promoting relevant programs to captivate learners' interest. Such autonomous capacities include; self-efficacy, volition, self-regulation and self-authorship which could be achieved by creating students' opportunities to be more productive thereby, fostering their confidence in achieving desired goals. Disseminating these findings to lecturers, students, educational administrators, guidance counselors, and other stakeholders of education may be a necessary way to increasingly turn the current lack of attention on the challenges faced by emerging adults in universities.

REFERENCES

1. Ada, P. (2010). Principles of Teaching. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis* 9(4), 337-343.
2. Ahlfeldt, S., Mehta, S., & Sellnow, T. (2005). Measurement and analysis of student engagement in university classes where varying levels of PBL methods of instruction are in use. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 24(1), 5-20.
3. Alrashidi, O., Phan, H. P., & Ngu, B. H. (2016). Academic engagement: an overview of its definitions, dimensions, and major conceptualisations. *International Education Studies*,

- 9(12), 41-52.
4. Appleton, K. (2008). Developing science pedagogical content knowledge through mentoring elementary teachers. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 19(6), 523-545.
 5. Appleton, J. J., Christenson, S. L., & Furlong, M. J. (2008). Student engagement with school: Critical conceptual and methodological issues of the construct. *Psychology in the Schools*, 45(5), 369-386.
 6. Assor, A., Roth, G., & Deci, E. L. (2004). The emotional costs of parents' conditional regard: A Self-Determination Theory analysis. *Journal of personality*, 72(1), 47-88.
 7. Arnett, J. J. (2000). Emerging adulthood: A theory of development from the late teens through the twenties. *American psychologist*, 55(5), 469.
 8. Arnett, J. J., & Taber, S. (1994). Adolescence terminable and interminable: When does adolescence end?. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 23(5), 517-537.
 9. Arnett, J. J., & Schwab, J. (2012). *The Clark University poll of emerging adults: Thriving, struggling, and hopeful*. Worcester, MA: Clark University.
 10. Jensen Arnett, J. (2015). Socialization in emerging adulthood: From the family to the wider world, from socialization to self-socialization.
 11. Ballou, K. A. (1998). A concept analysis of autonomy. *Journal of professional nursing*, 14(2), 102-110.
 12. Barro, R. J., & Lee, J. W. (2010). *A New Data Set of Educational Attainment in the World, 1950-2010*. NBER Working Paper No. 15902. National Bureau of Economic Research.
 13. Baxter Magolda, M. B. (2004). Evolution of a constructivist conceptualization of epistemological reflection. *Educational Psychologist*, 39(1), 31-42.
 14. Biya, P. (2009). *End of Year Address to the Nation*.
 15. Benson, P. (2008). Teachers' and learners' perspectives on autonomy. *Learner and teacher autonomy*, 15-32.
 16. Bergman, B. G., Kelly, J. F., Nargiso, J. E., & McKowen, J. W. (2016). "The Age of Feeling in-Between": Addressing Challenges in the Treatment of Emerging Adults With Substance Use Disorders. *Cognitive and behavioral practice*, 23(3), 270-288.
 17. Bea, M. D., & Yi, Y. (2019). Leaving the financial nest: Connecting young adults' financial independence to financial security. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 81(2), 397-414.
 18. Beck, U. (2002). *Individualization: Institutionalized individualism and its social and political consequences (Vol. 13)*. Sage.
 19. Bonanno, G. A., Wortman, C. B., Lehman, D. R., Tweed, R. G., Haring, M., Sonnega, J., ... & Nesse, R. M. (2002). Resilience to loss and chronic grief: a prospective study from preloss to 18-months postloss. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 83(5), 1150.
 20. Brown, T. A., & Barlow, D. H. (2009). A proposal for a dimensional classification system based on the shared features of the DSM-IV anxiety and mood disorders: implications for assessment and treatment. *Psychological assessment*, 21(3), 256.
 21. Buckley, P. J., Pass, C. L., & Prescott, K. (1988). Measures of international

- competitiveness: a critical survey. *Journal of marketing management*, 4(2), 175-200.
22. Budwig, N., & Alexander, A. J. (2020). A transdisciplinary approach to student learning and development in university settings. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 576250.
 23. Carter, R. W. G. (2013). *Coastal environments: an introduction to the physical, ecological, and cultural systems of coastlines*. Elsevier.
 24. Carini, R. M., Kuh, G. D., & Klein, S. P. (2006). Student engagement and student learning: Testing the linkages. *Research in higher education*, 47, 1-32.
 25. Call, K. T., Riedel, A. A., Hein, K., McLoyd, V., Petersen, A., & Kipke, M. (2002). Adolescent health and well-being in the twenty-first century: a global perspective. *Journal of research on adolescence*, 12(1), 69-98.
 26. Coaldrake, P., & Stedman, L. (1999). *Academic work in the twenty-first century*. Canberra, Higher Education Division, Training and Youth Affairs
 27. Castillo, L. G., & Schwartz, S. J. (2013). Introduction to the special issue on college student mental health. *Journal of clinical psychology*, 69(4), 291-297.
 28. Coole, D. (2016). Women in political theory. In *Democracy: A Reader* (pp. 307-314). Columbia University Press
 29. Côté, J. E., & Levine, C. G. (2014). *Identity, formation, agency, and culture: A social psychological synthesis*. Psychology Press.
 30. Credé, M., & Niehorster, S. (2012). Adjustment to college as measured by the student adaptation to college questionnaire: A quantitative review of its structure and relationships with correlates and consequences. *Educational Psychology Review*, 24, 133-165.
 31. D'Souza, L. (2016). *A Study of the Educational Approach of Don Bosco as Implemented in the Schools of the Western Region of India* (Doctoral dissertation, Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda (India)).
 32. Eccles, J. S., & Templeton, J. (2002). Chapter 4: Extracurricular and other after-school activities for youth. *Review of research in education*, 26(1), 113-180.
 33. Erikson, K. (2006). The constructive developmental theory of Robert Kegan. *The Family Journal*, 14(3), 290-298.
 34. Evans, N. J., Forney, D. S., Guido, F. M., Patton, L. D., & Renn, K. A. (2010). Racial identity development. *Student development in college: Theory, research and practice*, 2, 260-261.
 35. Finlay, L. (2006). 'Rigour', 'ethical integrity' or 'artistry'? Reflexively reviewing criteria for evaluating qualitative research. *British Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 69(7), 319-326.
 36. Flinders, D. J., & Thornton, S. J. (2013). Introduction to part two. *The curriculum studies*
 37. Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of educational research*, 74(1), 59-109.
 38. Friedman, S. R., Rapport, L. J., Lumley, M., Tzelepis, A., VanVoorhis, A., Stettner, L., & Kakaati, L. (2003). Aspects of social and emotional competence in adult attention-

- deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Neuropsychology*, 17(1), 50.
39. Garette, B., & Dussauge, P. (2000). Alliances versus acquisitions: choosing the right option. *European Management Journal*, 18(1), 63-69.
 40. Gaus, G. F. (2005). The place of autonomy within liberalism. *Autonomy and the challenges to liberalism: New essays*, 272-306.
 41. Christman, J. (2004). Relational autonomy, liberal individualism, and the social constitution of selves. *Philosophical Studies: An International Journal for Philosophy in the Analytic Tradition*, 117(1/2), 143-164.
 42. Gutek, G. L. (2014). Maria Montessori: Contributions to educational psychology. In *Educational Psychology* (pp. 171-186). Routledge.
 43. Hart, S. R., Stewart, K., & Jimerson, S. R. (2011). The student engagement in schools questionnaire (SESQ) and the teacher engagement report form-new (TERF-N): Examining the preliminary evidence. *Contemporary School Psychology: Formerly "The California School Psychologist"*, 15(1), 67-79.
 44. Hertz, J. E. (1996). Conceptualization of perceived enactment of autonomy in the elderly. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*, 17(3), 261-273.
 45. Hodge, D. C., Baxter Magolda, M. B., & Haynes, C. A. (2009). Engaged learning: Enabling self-authorship and effective practice. *Liberal Education*, 95(4), 16-23.
 46. Honwana, A., & De Boeck, F. (2005). *Makers & breakers: Children and youth in postcolonial Africa*. James Currey.
 47. Hu, Y. L., Ching, G. S., & Chao, P. C. (2012). Taiwan student engagement model: Conceptual framework and overview of psychometric properties. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 1(1), 69-90.
 48. Jensen, L. A., Arnett, J. J., & McKenzie, J. (2011). *Globalization and cultural identity* (pp. 285-301). Springer New York.
 49. Johnson, D. W. (1991). *Cooperative Learning: Increasing College Faculty Instructional Productivity*. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 4, 1991. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Reports, George Washington University, One Dupont Circle, Suite 630, Washington, DC 20036-1183.
 50. Kabeer, N. (1999). Resources, agency, achievements: Reflections on the measurement of women's empowerment. *Development and change*, 30(3), 435-464.
 51. Kant, I. (2001). *Lectures on ethics* (Vol. 2). Cambridge University Press
 52. Killmister, S. (2017). Dignity: Personal, social, human. *Philosophical Studies*, 174, 2063-2082.
 53. Keniston, L. (2000). Two distinctive antinociceptive systems in rats with pathological pain. *Neuroscience letters*, 280(1), 13-16.
 54. Koepke, S., & Denissen, J. J. (2012). Dynamics of identity development and separation-individuation in parent-child relationships during adolescence and emerging adulthood—A conceptual integration. *Developmental review*, 32(1), 67-88.
 55. Kloppenborg, J. T. (1987). *The virtues of liberalism: Christianity, republicanism, and*

- ethics in early American political discourse. *The Journal of American History*, 74(1), 9-33
56. Kupfer, J. (1987). Privacy, autonomy, and self-concept. *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 24(1), 81-89.
 57. Levin, H. M. (2013). The utility and need for incorporating noncognitive skills into large-scale educational assessments. *The role of international large-scale assessments: Perspectives from technology, economy, and educational research*, 67-86.
 58. Lickona, T. (1999). Character education: The cultivation of virtue. *Instructional-design theories and models: A new paradigm of instructional theory*, 2, 591-612.
 59. Lillard, A. S., Lerner, M. D., Hopkins, E. J., Dore, R. A., Smith, E. D., & Palmquist, C. M. (2013). The impact of pretend play on children's development: a review of the evidence. *Psychological bulletin*, 139(1), 1.
 60. Lo-oh, J. L. (2016). The role of social support in the future orientation of emerging adults in Cameroon. *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences Vol*, 4(7).
 61. Maysel, O., & Keren, E. (2014). Finding a meaningful life as a developmental task in emerging adulthood: The domains of love and work across cultures. *Emerging Adulthood*, 2(1), 63-73.
 62. Moshman, D. (2005). *Adolescent psychological development: Rationality, morality, and identity*. Psychology Press.
 63. Murray, A. W. (2004). Recycling the cell cycle: cyclins revisited. *Cell*, 116(2), 221-234.
 64. Musengi, M., & Shumba, A. (2013). Access to sexuality information by Zimbabwean school teenagers. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 23(2), 335-337.
 65. Nsamenang, A. B. (2002). Adolescence in Sub-Saharan Africa: An image constructed from Africa's triple inheritance. *The world's youth: Adolescence in eight regions of the globe*, 61-104.
 66. Nsamenang, A. B. (2008). Culture and human development. *International Journal of Psychology*, 43(2), 73-77.
 67. Nucci, L. P. (2001). *Education in the moral domain*. Cambridge University Press.
 68. Pinker, S., & Ullman, M. T. (2002). The past and future of the past tense. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 6(11), 456-463.
 69. Pizzolato, J. E. (2007). Impossible selves: Investigating students' persistence decisions when their career-possible selves border on impossible. *Journal of Career Development*, 33(3), 201-223.
 70. Pizzolato, J. E., & Ozaki, C. C. (2007). Moving toward self-authorship: Investigating outcomes of learning partnerships. *Journal of College Student Development*, 48(2), 196-214.
 71. Prunkl, C. (2022). Human autonomy in the age of artificial intelligence. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 4(2), 99-101.
 72. Rosich, G. (2019). *The Contested History of Autonomy: Interpreting European Modernity*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

73. Rushworth, M. F. S., Walton, M. E., Kennerley, S. W., & Bannerman, D. M. (2004). Action sets and decisions in the medial frontal cortex. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 8(9), 410-417.
74. Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 25(1), 54-67.
75. Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2001). On happiness and human potentials: A review of research on hedonic and eudaimonic well-being. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 141-166.
76. Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2006). Self-regulation and the problem of human autonomy: Does psychology need choice, self-determination, and will?. *Journal of personality*, 74(6), 1557-1586.
77. Schulenberg, J. E., & Maggs, J. L. (2002). A developmental perspective on alcohol use and heavy drinking during adolescence and the transition to young adulthood. *Journal of Studies on Alcohol, Supplement*, (14), 54-70.
78. Shernoff, D. J., Csikszentmihalyi, M., Shneider, B., & Shernoff, E. S. (2003). Student engagement in high school classrooms from the perspective of flow theory. *School psychology quarterly*, 18(2), 158.
79. Shepard, L. (2001). The role of classroom assessment in teaching and learning.
80. Schulenberg, J. E., & Zarrett, N. R. (2006). *Mental Health During Emerging Adulthood: Continuity and Discontinuity in Courses, Causes, and Functions*.
81. Skinner, B. F. (1971). Operant conditioning. *The encyclopedia of education*, 7, 29-33.
82. Smith, J. S., & Wertlieb, E. C. (2005). Do first-year college students' expectations align with their first-year experiences?. *NASPA journal*, 42(2), 153-174.
83. Stoljar, N. (2011). Informed consent and relational conceptions of autonomy. *Journal of Medicine and Philosophy*, 36(4), 375-384.
84. Tchombe, T. M. (2020). Chapter Ten Teaching of Psychology: The Case Of Some Cameroon Universities Therese Ms Tchombe. *Teaching Psychology around the World: Volume 5*, 5, 118.
85. Theobald, N. A., & Haider-Markel, D. P. (2009). Race, bureaucracy, and symbolic representation: Interactions between citizens and police. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 19(2), 409-426.
86. Teneng, P. P. (2016). Skills Oriented Higher Education and Graduate Employability in Cameroon: The Case of the National Employment Fund. *International Journal of New Technology and Research (IJNTR)*, 2(5), 26-29.
87. Van Gundy, K. (2002). Gender, the assertion of autonomy, and the stress process in young adulthood. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 346-363
88. Vansteenkiste, M., & Beyers, W. (2013). The jingle-jangle fallacy in adolescent autonomy in the family: In search of an underlying structure. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 42, 994-1014.
89. Weinstein, N., & Ryan, R. M. (2010). When helping helps: autonomous motivation for prosocial behavior and its influence on well-being for the helper and recipient. *Journal*

of personality and social psychology, 98(2), 222.

90. Wehmeyer, M. L., & Bolding, N. (2001). Enhanced self-determination of adults with intellectual disability as an outcome of moving to community-based work or living environments. *Journal of intellectual disability research*, 45(5), 371-383.
91. Williams, M. K. (2017). John Dewey in the 21st century. *Journal of Inquiry and Action in Education*, 9(1), 7.